

Generation of apical-out enteroids

Note1: for the reagents refer to “List of reagents for enteroid protocols” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13847508)

Note2: Grow enteroids in CM without nicotinamide. In this condition enteroids assume a more spherical shape

- 1) Add 500 μ L 5 mM EDTA/PBSL to each 24-well plate of 3D enteroids embedded in Geltrex™. Pipette up and down with P1000 pipette for 5-6 times
- 2) Transfer the solution from up to 4 wells into a 15 ml tube containing 8-10 mL of ice cold 5 mM EDTA/PBSL
- 3) Incubate tubes on a rocking platform, on ice, for 45'
- 4) Spin enteroids at 300 rcf for 3' at 4°C
- 5) Remove EDTA/PBSL and add DMEM/F12
- 6) Spin at 300 rcf for 3' at 4°C
- 7) Resuspend enteroids in the appropriate amount of CM (30 enteroids in 500 μ L of CM)
- 8) Transfer 500 μ L of enteroid suspension into each well of a 24 well ultra-low attachment plate (cls 3473_24EA, Corning)
- 9) Incubate for 2-5 days in incubator at 37°C in a 5% CO₂